

Prevalence of diarrhea in local population of Bagh City, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Study on the Diarrheal disease prevalence was conducted in the city Bagh, extending from March to August 2017. Diarrhea cause most infection in children as well as adult in the world. To assess the prevalence of disease in city, all public and private hospitals were visited for the collection of data. The highest number of infected children, 471 was found in the month of April and 462 August but least numbers, 191 in the month of March.

Keywords: Diarrhea, Bagh, Children, Prevalence

INTRODUCTION

Diseases are common in Pakistan, due to unhygienic condition; people suffer in different diseases. The people use traditional health care and modern medicine to treat diseases (Fabricant and Farnsworth, 2001; Umair and Yaqoob, 2018; Adil and Tariq, 2020; Altaf *et al.*, 2020; Aslam and Faiz, 2020; Mughal *et al.*, 2020; Tariq, 2020; Abbasi, 2021; Altaf *et al.*, 2021; Haidar and Bashir, 2021; Ijaz and Faiz, 2021; Ijaz and Iftikhar, 2021; Saleem *et al.*, 2021; Zainab, 2021). Diarrheal disease is the most common disease of childhood, mostly affect the children below the age of 5 year in advance countries (Walker *et al.*, 2013). Studies have shown that in the developing countries like Ethiopia, Africa and South Asia Diarrhea cause most deaths of children under 5 years age. In Ethiopia, both in urban and rural areas children death rate is thirteen per cent. Diarrhea mostly affects the children having the age of 6 to 23 months. It estimates that 2.5 million children die due to Diarrheal disease each year, only in Africa 800,000 children die each year (Walker *et al.*, 2009).

In Cameroon Diarrhea cause morbidity and death of many children because Diarrhea is a biggest public health issue (Nguendo *et al.*, 2008). The effect of diarrhea varies in age as well as seasons. Diarrhea is second major leading cause of death of children after malaria. Previous studies show that Diarrhea morbidity has direct link with geographical zones because different zones of the world have different socioeconomic as well as topographical condition. Some urban and rural zones are poor and other very rich. Measles immunization mostly related with Diarrheal morbidity (Arif and Ibrahim, 1998).

Diarrheal disease is caused due to shortage of clean drinking water, no proper way to dispose human feces, insufficient feeding pattern, grimy house condition, lake of proper medical facilities (Nguendo *et al.*, 2008). Diarrhea causes 80 per cent deaths in first two year of life. Mostly food and water pathogens cause diarrheal diseases. Diarrhea causes two thirds of total annual death of children of 5 year old in Pakistan (Arif and Ibrahim, 1998). Main objectives of study were as; to assess the prevalence of Diarrheal disease in the population of city Bagh during the study period and to know the monthly rate of infection in the study area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

During the present study, all public and private hospitals of the city Bagh was visited for gleaning maximum information about the patients suffering from Diarrheal disease discussed the study plan with the hospital administrations for the collection of data. The visit plan was devised after consultation with hospital administration. The strategy was devised to visit each hospital twice a month for getting data from all the public and private hospitals. So the each hospital visited according to the plan for the all collection of data. Hospital wise tables were made for proper and correct tabulation of data to avoid the ambiguity in future compilation.

Each month twice collected information was entered into the relevant table for impending outcomes. In the Bagh city there are total 5 hospitals, one under District administration, District Head Quarter Hospital, one under military establishment and three private hospitals, Allied, Alshifa, Al-Latif hospital. Data has been collected from the selected health units of the Bagh city from March to August 2017. Visits were made to all hospitals on weekly bases.

RESULTS AND DISSCUSION

The data of the present study was collected during the spring and rainy season from March to August, 2017, August is the heart of rainy season, diarrhea wide spread occurrence has been reported during this months. The total population of Bagh is 371919 individuals and Diarrhea patients recorded during the study period are 1888. This study shows the wide spread occurrence of childhood Diarrhea among the children under the age of 5 years old is 0.507 percent. During the month of March 191 patients visited the DHQ hospital for treatment, MDS most cases have been observed in month of April 471 and August 462. But less numbers observed in month of March only 191. It has been observed the most Diarrhea patient prefer to get treatment from DHQ hospital Bagh (Table 1-6).

Table 1: Data from DHQ hospital Bagh AJ&K

Month	Number of patient (0-5) year
March	51
April	136
May	54
June	35
July	76
August	172

Table 2: Data from Allied hospital Bagh AJ&K

Month	Number of patient (0-5) year
March	12
April	24
May	58
June	73
July	80
August	66

Table 3: Data from Al-Shifa hospital Bagh AJ&K

Month	Number of patient (0-5) year
March	61
April	93
May	18
June	44
July	29
August	38

Table 4: Data from Al-Latif hospital Bagh AJ&K

Month	Number of patient (0-5) year
March	11
April	169
May	89
June	37
July	28
August	19

Table 5: Data from MDS hospital Bagh AJ&K

Month	Number of patient (0-5) year
March	56
April	49
May	32
June	98
July	13
August	167

Table 6: Monthly data

Month	No of patient	Percentage
March	191	0.05%
April	471	0.12%
May	251	0.06%
June	287	0.07%
July	226	0.06%
August	462	0.12%

It has been observed that patients are also giving preference to get treatment from MDS hospital (415) and then Al-Latif (353) and Allied (313) and few patients, go to Alshifa hospital bagh (283). Greater the number of infected children during the month of April and August may be due the abundance of flies in these months, flies are vector of many diseases (Oslen, 1998). In the district Bagh, during the month of April and August rain fall is greater than other month of year

(Bashar, 1987). There is dire need to address the health issue particularly regarding to children health, neonatal death rate can be curbed by taking preventing measures both by parents, sanitation department and health authorities. Mother education and provision of better health services to children is pivotal for lowering mortality rate. This is compulsory to implement the health care practice to address child care problems in Bagh as well as in Azad Kashmir. The implementation of health practices and programs needs to be intensified for decreasing the major loss of childhood deaths. The inequality prevalence rate of disease may be due to seasonal changes.

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